

On-demand Trial Networks over 6G-SANDBOX infrastructure

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Abstract—The transition from 5G to 6G technologies needs comprehensive experimental infrastructure to serve as early placeholders for validation of 6G Technologies as Proof of Concepts. Such infrastructure is vital for demonstrating the benefits of these technologies in terms of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs), employing a repeatable and automatable testing methodology. However, the prohibitive cost of constructing proprietary testbeds for validation poses a significant challenge for many institutions. This underscores the imperative for shared, cost-effective experimental infrastructure that is accessible under reasonable conditions and capable of continuous upgrades to accommodate evolving 6G innovations.

Addressing this challenge, the 6G-SANDBOX project offers a solution through the design and implementation of a testing facility that automates the processes of definition, deployment, and experimentation with ad-hoc end-to-end networks. Within this framework, Trial Networks are fully manageable and configurable mobile end-to-end networks created to support one or several experiments by multiple users over a shared infrastructure. The primary advantage of the 6G-SANDBOX approach lies in its automation and orchestration capabilities, specifically the zero-touch provisioning of secure, low-cost experimental testbeds and the capabilities to repeat experiments as needed. This empowers experimenters of various profiles to conduct short to long-term experimentation campaigns with low investment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Building and exposing experimental testbeds for 5G has been addressed by 5G PPP projects [1], and by other international and national programmes like FIRE [2] in Europe, PAWR in the US [3] and 5GTN in Finland [4]. However, these previous approaches have two main blocking points to full-fill the requirements expected by experimenters in the 5G and 6G domains. The first obstacle is free access to the internal configuration of the network components, for instance to test new AI/ML algorithms for any optimization at network or service level. The second one is high availability to run medium or long term experimentation works, or even complete projects, without time-consuming manual reconfiguration and provisioning of the setup from time to time. Both aspects are related to the capability of the underlying infrastructure to automatically support pure automation and orchestration of the multi-tenancy platforms in a secured manner. Addressing both gaps towards a more *industrialized (automated-repeatable)* way of providing 6G testbeds will benefit both the experimenters and the platform owners.

Such automated and secure multi-tenancy support for experimenters in the same shared infrastructure is related to the concepts of Testbed as a Service and Network Slicing, that has been addressed in projects such as Géant Testbed Service (GTS) [5], EuWireless [6] and SLICES [7]. GTS was mainly oriented to creating a network of interconnected virtual machines across Europe supported by the Géant Research Infrastructure. The EuWireless proposal is to offer each experimenter a virtual testbed composed of shared resources from a number of point of presence across Europe coming from academic and mobile operators. SLICES is defining a long term ESFRI European wide infrastructure to support research in computation and communication, with 5G as a subset. All these projects consider some kind of API or language to define the slice as a full end-to-end network built from shared resources and available for the experimenter in a remote manner.

6GSANDBOX takes this concept further by adopting new industry trends from IT to manage **Infrastructure as Code** (IaC). IaC enables the automation and repetitiveness needed adding *idempotency* to the result. To embrace the IaC concept, 6GSANDBOX relies on IT tools such as Terraform¹ to achieve the results.

In this context, 6G-SANDBOX proposes a framework to automate the generation of isolated and independent *testbeds* as *Trial Networks (TNS)*. A Trial Network (TN) is part of an actual testbed on a shared multi-tenancy infrastructure reserved for one experimenter to perform short or long term end-to-end validations of technologies and services, mainly to report key performance indicators (KPIs). A Trial Network is fully configurable, manageable and controllable end-to-end network (including slicing capabilities) which combine digital and physical nodes to validate new technologies and research advancements towards 6G. Within the Trial Network, the experimenter will have access to configuration, monitoring and deployment, as well as support to automate the experimentation work. 6G-SANDBOX will provide a description language and APIs to define the Trial Network as code and will implement a fully automated multi-tenancy infrastructure to expand experimentation on 6G to multiple experimenters with different needs in terms of technologies, uses cases and project duration.

6G-SANDBOX focuses on 6G considering that the experimenters (both technology providers and service

¹<https://www.terraform.io/>

Trial Network Life Cycle Manager

Fig. 1: High level concept of a Trial Network and its life cycle.

providers) require that Trial Networks provide more flexibility for creation (including using Digital Twins of some components), more permissions for (re)configuration (including AI/ML based end to end configuration and slicing), long term availability (even in a discontinuous form), and APIs to connect their (on premises) ad-hoc devices or software.

This paper presents the Trial Network concept and current implementation. Section II elaborates on the concept of Trial Network Life Cycle as the main product to be exposed to experimenters. Section III presents the description language to define TNs with the components in the 6G-Library and the implementation of the whole approach. Section IV summarizes the next steps and provide some conclusions.

II. THE CONCEPT OF TRIAL NETWORK

Trial Networks is one particular approach to slicing in the network that refers to all the elements needed for advanced experimentation. It is beyond 3GPP slicing because it includes the deployment of new network components on demand with specific typologies and resources. As represented in Figure 1, TNs is closer to the approaches defined in projects like Geant Testbed Service and EuWireless. The idea is to develop a software framework that comprises network elements based on the definition by the user, connect them and produce a fully functional network. Geant Testbed Service focused on virtual machines as components all across Europe. EuWireless expanded this idea with mobile network elements, but only carried out the design study. 6G-SANDBOX refines the approach and provides a large scale implementation.

A Trial Network in 6G-SANDBOX is a full end-to-end 5G/6G network that consist of virtualized resources

(computing, storage), connectivity (networks, radio configurations) and devices (UEs, measurement equipment), isolated from other Trial Networks, and that can persist for an undetermined amount of time.

Figure 1 represents one experimental 5G/6G platform with several active TNs (running) and several suspended TNs. The whole platform is managed, updated and operated by the platform operator. The TNs are created, managed and destroyed on request by the TN owners, who delegates access to experimentation to TN experimenters. Typical TN owners are project coordinators managing a number of experimenters (for instance the Stream D projects in the European SNS JU). Typical TN experimenters are academic or industrial researchers or application developers. The number of active and suspended TNs depends on the availability of resources and the specific need of the experimenters at any given time. The platform implements resource management and scheduling to optimize the service. The Life Cycle of the Trial Network represented in top part of Figure 1 works as follows.

The process starts with the *create* request by the TN owner who provides a formal definition of the Trial Network, possibly in cooperation with the TN experimenter. The Trial Networks are defined by means of a descriptor file (described in section III-A). A catalog of templates is provided to facilitate the creation of the file. This process is well-documented and automated, to shorten creation and customization of Trial Networks from weeks to hours or minutes.

A key component in 6G-SANDBOX is the *pre-testing* or verification module that ensures that the 6G Trial Networks defined in TN Descriptors are fully tested before deployment. Aspects such as internal connectivity, experimenter

accessibility, security, performance and other KPIs and absence of unexpected situations are statically checked before allowing experimenters to start the Trial Network. If issues are detected, these are reported to the experimenter so that they can be corrected before proceeding.

The *deployment* of a 6G Trial Network means the actual deployment of software and the interconnection and configuration of instances of the components (network functions and devices) to obtain a full end-to-end working network. The descriptions of the TN software and hardware components are centrally stored in a dedicated repository, denoted as the 6G-Library within the project framework. The 6G-Library is managed by a number of 6G-SANDBOX points of deployment (PODs) across Europe. Current PODs are the 4 6G-SANDBOX platforms in Athens, Berlin, Malaga and Oulu. Optionally, the TN can include resources provided by the experimenter, potentially on premises. Experimenters can request that, during deployment, that the TN is also be equipped with existing experimentation and automation support available from previous projects, such as the Open 5Genesis Suite [8].

After initial deployment, the TN is *suspended*. On request by an authorized experimenter, the TN can become *active* to have resources available for the experimenter. The *scheduling* of a TNs performs the same work as the computer’s operating system to manage the life cycle of a process and share resources while ensuring priorities and deadlines. The TN can be temporally suspended by the 6G-SANDBOX initiative or upon a request by the experimenter or the owner, activated or terminated in a normal form or because of some unexpected failure. For instance, the lack of human experimenter interaction for a long time could fire suspension. Stable configurations, apart from the initial one, can be saved and further selected as a valid TN.

The *reconfiguration* is requested by the TN owner to optimize or to change topology or parameters. In the same direction, one specific case of reconfiguration is the upgrade. Considering that the availability and feature set of the 6G components will change over time (for instance due to results in the JU SNS projects), the management of a Trial Network itself will be a case of hybrid CI/CD (Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery) that applies to the software and the hardware, where experimenters can have updates always running the most recent version of the components, but with track changes support so that they can return to previous versions, for comparison or in case of issues.

III. DEFINITION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE TN

Figure 2 represents the whole 6G-SANDBOX architecture described in Deliverable 2.1 of the project², with TNs in the central position. The lower part of the picture represents the actual hardware and software available in the project platforms (currently Athens, Berlin, Malaga and Oulu). This level of resources is managed by the Trial Network Life Cycle Manager (TNLCM) to reserve, connect, configure and in general manage the life cycle of the TN described above. At this level, the catalogue of resources is defined in the

Fig. 2: Architecture of 6G-SANDBOX facility.

public 6G-Library. Users have two levels of interaction with the Trial Networks:

- 1) Definition and onboarding of the Trial Network in the platform, and subsequent actions to manage its life cycle as a whole (pause, resume, etc. the Trial Network),
- 2) Interaction with the separate elements that form the Trial Network, either manually using the available interfaces for each component, or, optionally, through the use of a pre-deployed set of experimentation tools provided by 6G-SANDBOX, such as the Experiment Life Cycle Manager [8] or the Path-Wave Test Automation from Keysight³. Advanced experimenters may also choose to deploy any experimentation tool or software component that they deem necessary, for example, manually configuring all the software components in a “plain” TN.

Code 1 shows the roles of the TNLCM and 6G-Library in the overall process of TN management. More details will be provided in subsequent sections.

```
# Trial Network Descriptor Schema
Trial Network:
<Entity1>: #identifier for each entity in the TN.
  Type: #component type in the 6G-Library.
  Model: #specific physical device or subtype of
  component.
  Expose: #values that should be provided to
  experimenters.
  Parameters: #values to specify to customize the
  entity.
  <Parameter1>: <Value1>
  # ...
  Connections: #dependencies presented by the entity
  with regard to other components.
  <Connection1>: <EntityN>.<Interface1>
  # ...
  Monitor: #for probes, list of entities to monitor.
  - EntityN
  Store: #values to keep after deletion of the TN.
```

Code 1: Trial Network Descriptor Schema.

A. The TN description language

A TN is defined by the TN owner with a language that describes the composition of the network with components

²More details at <https://6g-sandbox.eu/dissemination/deliverables/>

³<https://www.keysight.com>

from the 6G-Library. The life cycle of a TN starts with the creation of a Trial Network Descriptor (TND), which includes information about the elements that must be accessible or instantiated as part of a TN and their configurations, the topology of the network and the expected interconnection between the elements, as well as any other information that further describe the behavior and details of the Trial Network. The schema that follows the definition of a TND is shown in the Code 1, which includes the description of each element as comments. A catalog of pre-defined TNDs for common use cases will be made available as part of the 6G-Library. Said TNDs follow the above schema and can be used as a base for further customization or instantiated directly as ready-to-use TNs.

An example of TND file is shown in Code 2. This is a yaml file which includes components such as DataNetwork, Phone, RU (Remote Head), DU (Distributed Unit), CU (Control Unit), RIC (Realtime controller), gNB, SMO, Core and Terminal. Note that the terminal component has “ALL” in the field interface. This means that the terminal is connected to all the components via the “Bastion”. A Bastion is a mandatory component implementing routing capabilities which is added by default to all TNs to ensure internal an external secured connectivity (not included in the TND). The Figure 3 shows the connections and the dependencies between the components described in the Trial Network Descriptor.

```
# Trial Network Descriptor (TND)
Trial Network:
  DataNetwork:
    Type: IPv4
    IP: 10.0.0.150
    Size: 10
    Gateway: 10.0.0.1
  Phone:
    Type: Android UE
    Model: S20
    Expose: [DeviceId, AdbServer]
  RU:
    Type: O-RU
    Parameters:
      Power: 0 dBm
      CentralFrequency: 3700 MHz
  DU:
    Type: O-DU
    Connections:
      FrontEnd: RU
  CU:
    Type: O-CU
    Connections:
      FrontEnd: DU
  RIC:
    Type: RIC
    Connections:
      O-DU: DU
      O-CU: CU
    Expose: [xAppsAPI]
  gNB:
    Type: gNBFR1
    Connections:
      FrontEnd: Core
  SMO:
    Type: Non-RT RIC
    Connections:
      RIC: RIC
  Core:
    Type: Open5GS
    Connections:
      FrontEnd: CU
    Interfaces: [DataNetwork]
  Terminal:
    Type: VM
    Parameters:
      Image: Ubuntu 20.04
      Storage: 100 Gb
      RAM: 8 Gb
    Interfaces: [ALL]
```


Fig. 3: Trial Network generated from descriptor file specified in code 2.

Expose: [SSH]

Code 2: Example of Trial Network Descriptor.

An important part of the life cycle is the validation of the TND, which gives the experimenter the possibility of assessing the correctness of their descriptor before the actual instantiation and configuration of the TN components inside the actual experimentation platform. In addition, another important part of the TNLCM is that it must verify that the resources exist, check their availability and that they are sufficient to be deployed. At all times, the experimenter must be alerted to what is happening.

B. The 6G-Library

In this section, we present essential aspects of the 6G-Library, outlining the primary tools employed and the file structure utilized for storing objects within the library.

The objects housed in the 6G-Library are meticulously curated and designed to serve as foundational building blocks for constructing TNs. The 6G-Library is stored in GitHub⁴ to take advantage of the sophisticated version control system and the collaborative work expected from the 5G/6G community to produce network components.

Additionally, the concept of ‘Everything as Code (EaC)’ has gained prominence in software development and DevOps methodologies. EaC involves utilizing code to define and manage IT resources, encompassing principles such as Infrastructure as Code and Config as Code. This approach leverages the advantages of Git and EaC, thereby enhancing efficiency and scalability in software development. Each element within this library embodies the EaC philosophy, designed as self-contained unit equipped with the necessary automation and scripts for deployment within the 6G-SANDBOX platform.

To ensure a consistent and cohesive approach to component creation and smooth integration, a comprehensive set of predefined requirements and best practices has been instituted. The architectural blueprint of each component has undergone meticulous crafting, prioritizing simplicity, clarity, versatility, scalability, and adaptability. The suite of tools depicted in Figure 4 has been carefully selected to automate the creation and configuration of each component, thereby guaranteeing a seamless development and deployment process.

Terraform: This tool facilitates the creation of virtual infrastructure across private cloud providers, enabling the

⁴<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library>

Fig. 4: Overview of TNLCM and 6G-Library implementation.

setup of virtual networks, machines, containers, Kubernetes clusters, and more. Terraform streamlines the infrastructure provisioning process.

Ansible: Utilized for comprehensive component configuration, equipment setup and integration, Ansible enables fine-grained actions on Trial Network components. Its idempotent nature ensures reliability in configurations.

Jenkins: This tool serves as the Orchestrator for deploying components, executing deployment processes efficiently. Jenkins streamlines and automates deployment workflows.

Bash: Enabling scripting for standalone operations, Bash provides flexibility and customization in executing various operational tasks.

6G-Library components are stored in GitHub⁵. Components are stored in folders hanging from the main directory. Each component contains four folders:

Doc: Contains the Documentation of the component in markdown format to enable direct integration between third parties and the catalogue.

Public: This folder contains a *description.yaml* file and the *changelog.yaml* file describing the changes in the component.

Private: The Private folder contains the component's implementation. The file *values.yaml* contains the Private variables of the component. The file *manifest.yaml* contains the instructions for Terraform to deploy the component in the infrastructure.

Results: Contains contains the response templates that the component can use to inform the TNLCM of the results of different operations such as deployment, updating or deletion.

Private folder contains one folder per supported Cloud environment by the component. Terraform will select the appropriate Cloud environment files when deploying the 6G-Library object in a particular cloud. The cloud environment folder contains two additional folders:

cac: Contains files related to configuration automation. Three stages of configuration can be used: pre-configuration, install configuration and post-configuration.

iac: Contains files related to infrastructure definition.

With this structure, any 6G-Library object can be described independently and tested using the TNLCM. Objects

can define *dependencies* with other Objects that need to be deployed beforehand.

Code 3 is an example of a *description.yaml* file and illustrates the information required for each 6G-Library object.

```
component_name: "tn_bastion"
family: bootstrap
maintainers:
  - <jesus.maciasportela@telefonica.com>
version: 0.0.1
depends:
  - tn_vxlan (>= 0.0.1)
short_description: Bastion VM for a Trial Network
long_description: Bastion VM includes
  - DHCP server
  - NTP server
  - Public network masquerading
  - Port forwarding
  - DNS server
  - VPN Server
platforms: [one]
sites: [uma]
```

Code 3: Example of *description.yaml* file.

The most important information elements to define the 6G-Library component are:

- **component_name:** Name of the 6G-Library object.
- **version:** Version number of the component.
- **depends:** Dependencies with other 6G-Library objects.
- **platforms:** Cloud providers supported.
- **sites:** 6G-SANDBOX platforms that support this component.

6G-Library objects modeled in 6G-SANDBOX include among others Software components such as Mobile Cores, gNBs emulators, specific Network Functions such as UPFs, NEF or NWDAF, CAPIF Core Function, as well as Physical equipment that can be connected to TNs such as gNBs, ORAN CUs & DUs, Traffic generators, Traffic analyzers, Digital Twins equipment, UEs, Satellite backhaul, etc. The resources provided by the experimenter should be defined in the same way as the components in the 6G-Library.

C. The TNLCM

The TNLCM has been designed as a modular application, with the intention of making certain components easily replaceable or extended, while minimizing the effect of changes in other parts of the application. At the same time, there is an emphasis on re-usability, where several data structures and generic logic can be shared between the different components of the application. The TNLCM

⁵https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/6G-Library/tree/update_bastion/tn_bastionarchitecture is currently organized as follows:

Core: The Core component implements the basic logic for Trial Networks’s lifecycle of the and the functionality required for communicating with the Resource Management Layer. It’s responsible for exposing the REST API that other components of the TNLCM, platform owners and experimenters can use for creating, managing and inspecting Trial Networks. In addition, it handles the connection with Jenkins which is the Orchestrator to deploy components efficiently. It can also generate a report with the information received from Jenkins about the status of the deployed components to expose it to the experimenter.

Front-End: The Front-End included with the TNLCM is a web application tailored for use by the platform owners and, as such, will provide information and functionality for handling all the Trial Networks in the corresponding platform. To achieve this, the Front-End makes use of the APIs exposed by the Core component. Other Front-Ends, for example, a simplified one tailored for Experimenters or Trial Network owners can be developed by making use of the same APIs, either by an external developer or by the 6G-SANDBOX consortium.

Scheduler(s): Schedulers can make use of the APIs exposed by Core to automatically retrieve information about the status of one or more Trial Networks, and to make changes to the status or configuration of such Trial Networks. Multiple schedulers may be active at the same time, each accessing different Trial Networks, while also Trial Network owners may also use, manually or through a Front-End, same APIs for modifying and inspecting the status of their Trial Networks.

Playbook: The Playbook contains all the logic and workflow definitions required for interacting (i.e., creating, destroying, modifying, etc.) with any kind of Entity that may be part of a Trial Network. This information is contained in the 6G-Library, which the TNLCM references. The Playbook class encapsulates the logic required for creating snapshots of this information (so that an update in the 6G-Library does not inadvertently break functionality on an existing Trial Network), and for providing easy access to the different workflows.

Library: The Library encapsulates the logic for interacting with the 6G-Library. It currently supports accessing multiple git repositories, each containing the definition of several types of components, and abstracts the logic required for moving between different branches and commits, to retrieve the information corresponding to a single component.

The TNLCM is being implemented using version 3.11 of Python programming language. This language allows flexibility when it comes to integrating it with Docker and automating its deployment on the platforms. TNLCM is stored on GitHub⁶ which allows for version control. The repository contains separate folders for each mayor component, which can be executed independently while having access to the common definitions shared by multiple components. This organization was chosen as it leads to an easy deployment both directly in the host machine and as containerized components orchestrated using docker-compose.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The paper has described the 6G-SANDBOX approach to build a long term European 6G experimentation facility based on Trial Networks (TNs). The project is developing and open source solution that can be used in any 5G/6G experimental platform to offer Testbeds as a Service. The intention is to provide this way of creating testbeds to support many activities in the more than 50 projects in the European SNS JU program and beyond this programm.

Subsequent developments will include the incorporation of *twinning* capabilities into the Trial Network. This involves creating a digital twin of either the entire TN or specific components, allowing for the substitution of actual components or the initiation/continuation of experiments within a hybrid network.

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⁶<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/TNLCM>